

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES CLASSES

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Annotation. In this article reader can inform about the role, usage of communicative language teaching method in schools or in other educational institutions also, there are informations about advantages and disadvantages of this technique. Actually, communicative language teaching is a modern language teaching approach that prioritizes real-life communication and interaction in memorization and grammar. It aims to develop learners' communicative skills by engaging themselves in role plays, problem-solving skills, group discussions. For comparing with other methods, CLT encourages students to use the language actively and creatively, even they have some mistakes. Grammar and vocabularies are taught in context rather than through isolated rules. This approach can enhance confidence and practical language skills.

Key words: communicative language teaching, real-life communication, grammar, authentic, student-centered

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'quvchiga maktablar va boshqa ta'lim muassasalarida qo'llanilayotgan muloqotga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish metodining ahamiyati, uning foydalanish holatlari. Shu bilan birgalikda, ushbu texnologiyaning foydali hamda ba'zi kamchiliklari haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Aslida, kommunikativ til o'rgatish (CLT) – bu zamonaviy til o'rgatish usuli bo'lib, rejalashtirilgan yodlash va grammatikani o'rganishdan ko'ra, real hayotiy muloqot va o'zaro aloqani ustuvor qo'yadi. U talabalarining kommunikativ ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, rolli o'yinlar, muammolarni hal qilish va guruh munozaralari orqali o'rgatiladi. Boshqa usullarga qaraganda, CLT talabalarni tilni faol va ijodiy qo'llashga undaydi, hatto ular xatolar qilsalar ham. Grammatika va lug'at qoidalari orqali emas, balki real kontekstda o'rgatiladi. Ushbu yondashuv o'quvchida o'ziga ishonch va amaliy til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi, bu esa uni yanada samarali va tabiiy qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: muloqotga yo'naltirilgan metod, hayotiy muloqot, grammatika, tabiiy manba, o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение и применение коммуникативного метода обучения в школах и других учебных заведениях. Также приводится информация о его преимуществах и некоторых недостатках. На самом деле, коммуникативное обучение языку (CLT) — это современный метод преподавания, который ставит реальное общение и взаимодействие выше заучивания и изучения грамматики. Он направлен на развитие коммуникативных навыков учащихся путем их вовлечения в ролевые игры, решение проблемных задач и групповые обсуждения. В отличие от других методов, CLT поощряет студентов активно и творчески использовать язык, даже если они совершают ошибки. Грамматика и лексика изучаются в контексте, а не через изолированные правила. Этот подход способствует развитию уверенности и практических языковых навыков, делая обучение более эффективным и естественным.

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Ключевые слова: коммуникативный метод, живое общение, грамматика, аутентичный источник, ученико-ориентированный подход.

In today's world learning a new language especially English language becoming more important and globally as a result of this teaching methods should be developed and every teacher has to improve or adapt to their students and their levels. One of the most effective methods is communicative language teaching namely CLT that prioritizes communication and interaction, focuses on helping students communicate effectively in real-world situations rather than just memorizing grammar rules and vocabulary. This approach encouraging learners to develop fluency before focusing on accuracy. Actually, the concept and history of communicative language teaching has a long tradition in the field of English language teaching methods. CLT was developed during the 1960s and 1970s in Europe based on Hymes and Canale and Swain's theories of language teaching, referred to as "Communicative Competence" (CC) so British linguists and applied linguists mentioned as the "father of the communicative approach".

For implementing this method teachers must know and use in a right way key principles of CLT because they create an effective, engaging and practical language learning experience. Here are some examples of principles:

Communication as the main goal. Language exists for real-life communication and so one example of this situation that students practice ordering food at a restaurant or asking for directions from strange people in the street, instead of filling in grammar exercises because many students claim that this kind of tasks in grammar or memorizing vocabularies are so challenging and monotonous in the classrooms. In addition to this, language is social, so practicing with real people improves both comprehension and speaking skills.

Use of authentic materials. This kind of materials cover real-life materials like menus, news articles, podcasts and etc. they expose students to natural language instead of textbook-only contents. To give an example, instead of learning only from a scripted dialogue or podcasts, students listen to real interviews or watch native speakers interact because in many situations only media materials seem boring also, through native speakers speech they can adjust to their second language.

Student-centered learning. When students take an active role in learning, they retain information better and become more confident speakers owing to the fact that it can develop skills needed in the workplace and every-day life, helps students apply

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knowledge in practical ways or encourages teamwork and social interaction, helping students develop communication skills with everyone for instance, if they work in group projects, peer teaching and discussions, they can improve speaking and listening skills in a language class.

Fluency over accuracy. In real communication, being understood is more important than perfect grammar so prioritizing fluency helps students speak without fear such as one student saying, “yesterday, I do my homework.” Still communicates meaning, even if the tense wrong. Over time, accuracy improves naturally however it should be controlled by teacher otherwise, this kind of mistakes will be more and it may cause to turn daily-life mistakes so teacher must give attention or advises in a right way without any pressure.

Context-based learning. Learning vocabulary and grammar in context makes it more memorable and practical as the first example, instead of learning words in isolation or at home by repeating new words, students learn phrases like “can I have the bill?” in a restaurant setting. One of the advantages of this they learn vocabulary without difficulties and monotony, second one is they implement their new words to their daily routine. Actually, each principle ensures that learners develop real communication skills instead of just memorizing rules. Without these principles, students may struggle to use the language naturally and confidently in everyday situations.

Communicative language teaching method involves mutual relationship and mutual activeness so we can face some teaching techniques in CLT. Firstly, every teacher must inform about information gap activities in classroom, such as, learners are given different pieces of information and they have to communicate to complete a task: one student has a map, another has a bus schedule and the they must work together to plan a holiday trip. Second one is problem-solving tasks that groups solve real-world problems through discussion or by hand-made presentations, they may plan an eco-friendly city using given budget constraints. For instance, when we had integrated skills lesson at our university, teacher gave us project work about water problems, at that time in our group had a four student and we made water cycle instruction for understanding the nature, then made a poster presentation for problems and solutions. Here have an example:

Storytelling and picture descriptions are important for enhancing fluency and creativity between students as a result of describing pictures in their second language or telling a story from series of images or just in a specific topic. Example of another

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technique is that each student gets a different part of a story or article and must summarize it for their group - a mystery story, not a too long, is split into three parts: students share information to solve the case. This story is appropriate for new learners:

One day, Anna was walking in the park when she saw a wallet on the ground. She picked it up and looked inside. There was money and an ID card. The name on the card was “Michael Brown.”

Anna looked around but saw no one. She decided to take the wallet to the police station. On her way, she heard a man talking on the phone, saying, “I lost my wallet!”

Anna walked up to him and asked, “Are you Michael Brown?”

The man was surprised. “Yes, I am! How do you know?”

Anna smiled and gave him the wallet. Michael was very happy and said, “Thank you so much! You are very kind.”

These kinds of texts can enhance moral obligation and honesty in youngsters, additionally, benefits of CLT are that improving motivation since students see practical use for the language and developing cultural awareness across language learners through authentic materials and discussions. Even though people know its advantages, they should consider about some challenges for usage of communicative language teaching like that lack of structure- as a result of real-life communication some students struggle without clear grammar instruction; requires skilled teachers- teachers must manage conversations and provide effective feedbacks as mentioned above; classroom management- group activities can sometimes become chaotic because in group discussions or role-play activities every student try to participate in lesson. Nevertheless, if teacher and student implement this method effectively, it can lead to great results by means of starting with simple, structured conversations and gradually increase complexity, creating a safe environment where students feel comfortable making mistakes, balancing fluency and accuracy by providing grammar support when needed.

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